

Supplementary Table S1. Alphabetical list of the species with GenBank accession numbers of the nucleotide sequences used in this study

Species	COI	CytB	12S rRNA	16S rRNA	Mitogenome	Reference
<i>Anarhichas orientalis</i>					LC493930	Poulsen et al. 2019
<i>Bothrocara brunneum</i>	FJ164403 - FJ164412					Steinke et al. 2009
<i>Bothrocara brunneum</i>	GU440254					Hastings, Burton 2010
<i>Bothrocara brunneum</i>	JQ354019 - JQ354020					Elz et al. 2012
<i>Bothrocara brunneum</i>	KF929669					Bentley, Wiley 2013
<i>Bothrocara hollandi</i>	EU741721 - EU741724					Radchenko et al. 2009
<i>Bothrocara hollandi</i>	MK560725 - MK560727, MK560729- MK560738					Kim, Bae 2019
<i>Bothrocara hollandi</i>	KC748099					Kwun, Kim 2013
<i>Bothrocara hollandi</i>					MK069496	Kim et al. 2019
<i>Bothrocara molle</i>	GU440255					Hastings, Burton 2010
<i>Bothrocara molle</i>	FJ164413 - FJ164417					Steinke et al. 2009
<i>Bothrocara molle</i>	ON398538					Teramura et al. 2022
<i>Bothrocara molle</i>	MF956538 - MF956545					Robertson et al. 2017
<i>Bothrocara soldatovi</i>	EU741718 - EU741720					Radchenko et al. 2009
<i>Bothrocara zestum</i>	KF019350					Turanov et al. 2014
<i>Bothrocara zestum</i>	HQ704771 - HQ704772					Turanov et al. 2012
<i>Gymnelus viridis</i>					OR582699	Bemis et al. 2023b

<i>Leptoclinus maculatus</i>					KT004433	Swanburg et al. 2015
<i>Lycenchelys muraena</i>					AP018418	Kawato et al. 2017
<i>Lycenchelys sarsii</i>					LC493908	Poulsen et al. 2019
<i>Lycodes albonotatus</i>	EU380273 - EU380274				KT004433	Radchenko et al. 2008a
<i>Lycodes brevipes</i>	MW435051					Li et al. 2022
<i>Lycodes brevipes</i>	KF019351, KC751826 - KC751827					Turanov et al. 2014
<i>Lycodes brevipes</i>	JQ354197 - JQ354200					Elz et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes brevipes</i>	HQ704757 - HQ704759					Turanov et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes brevipes</i>	FJ164763 - FJ164766					Steinke et al. 2009
<i>Lycodes brevipes</i>					MK133251	Li et al. 2019a
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	KY570340 - KY570341					Elz et al. 2017
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	KF930085					Bentley, Wiley 2013
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	KF019352, KC751829 - KC751832					Turanov et al. 2014
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	JQ354202 - JQ354203					Elz et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	HQ704755					Turanov et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	GU440392					Hastings, Burton 2010
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	FJ164767 - FJ164775					Steinke et al. 2009
<i>Lycodes diapterus</i>	KC879734					Kukhlevskiy et al. 2013
<i>Lycodes diapterus beringi</i>					OR499730	Bemis et al. 2023a

<i>Lycodes esmarkii</i>	KC015591 - KC015594					McCusker et al. 2013
<i>Lycodes esmarkii</i>	JX008541					Baillon et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes esmarkii</i>					LC493918	Poulsen et al. 2019
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>	MW435057, MW435080					Li et al. 2022
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>	KF019353, KC751833 - KC751834					Turanov et al. 2014
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>	JQ354209 - JQ354212,					Elz et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>	HQ712609 - HQ712627, HM421744, HM421747					Mecklenburg et al. 2011
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>	HQ704762 - HQ704764					Turanov et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>	FJ164793 - FJ164800					Steinke et al. 2009
<i>Lycodes palearis</i>					OR582688	Bemis et al. 2023b
<i>Lycodes polaris</i>	MZ618851, MZ618868 - MZ618869					Turanov 2021
<i>Lycodes polaris</i>	HM400287 - HM400288, HM400290, HM400293, HM400296, HM400301, HQ712597, HQ712628 -					Mecklenburg et al. 2011

	HQ712639					
<i>Lycodes polaris</i>	KC015599					McCusker et al. 2013
<i>Lycodes polaris</i>	MW435072					Li et al. 2022
<i>Lycodes polaris</i>					MK910376	Li et al. 2019b
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>	MZ618853		MZ621060, MZ621099			Turanov 2021
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>	KF019354					Turanov et al. 2014
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>	HQ712640 - HQ712645, HM421770					Mecklenburg et al. 2011
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>	HQ704785 - HQ704788					Turanov et al. 2012
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>	EU380263 - EU380265	EU404177 - EU404179				Radchenko et al. 2008a
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>		KC751700 - KC751703				Turanov et al. 2013
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>				EU741757		Radchenko et al. 2009
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>			LC069626, LC069638			Miya, Sado, 2015
<i>Lycodes raridens</i>					MN604279	Lee et al. 2019
<i>Lycodes reticulatus</i>	MG680188					Gordeeva, 2017
<i>Lycodes reticulatus</i>	KC015600 - KC015601					McCusker et al. 2013
<i>Lycodes reticulatus</i>					LC493905	Poulsen et al. 2019
<i>Lycodes tanakae</i>	KC748104					Kwun, Kim 2013
<i>Lycodes tanakae</i>					KX148472	Kim et al. 2016
<i>Lycodes tanakae</i>					OR687549	Balakirev et al. in press
<i>Lycodes toyamensis</i>	EU741702 - EU741711					Radchenko et al. 2009
<i>Lycodes turneri</i>	HM421790					Mecklenburg et al. 2011

<i>Lycodes turneri</i>					OR499727	Bemis et al. 2023a
<i>Lycodes vahlii</i>	KJ128537 - KJ128538					Bergsten et al. 2014
<i>Lycodes vahlii</i>	KC015603 - KC015614					McCusker et al. 2013
<i>Lycodes vahlii</i>					MT410895	Margaryan et al. 2020
<i>Lycodes ygreknotatus</i>					LC093396	Zheng et al. 2019
<i>Melanostigma atlanticum</i>					LC493916	Poulsen et al. 2019
<i>Melanostigma gelatinosum</i>					OX456522	Wellcome Sanger Tree of Life Programme 2023
<i>Ophthalmolycus amberensis</i>	OK493633, OK493678 - OK493680, OK493724, OK493744					Cao et al. 2022
<i>Ophthalmolycus amberensis</i>	JN641042 - JN641043, JN641045 - JN641046, JN641177					Smith et al. 2011
<i>Ophthalmolycus amberensis</i>	HQ713099 - HQ713106					Dettaï et al. 2011
<i>Ophthalmolycus amberensis</i>					ON417737	Hotaling et al. 2023
<i>Ophthalmolycus amberensis</i>				JX974423		Rehbein 2012
<i>Ophthalmolycus sp.</i>	MF956905 - MF956912					Robertson et al. 2017
<i>Ophthalmolycus sp.</i>	KX676090 - KX676096					Mabragaña et al. 2016
<i>Petroschmidtia albonotatus</i>	LC514669					Sakuma 2019
<i>Petroschmidtia albonotatus</i>	LC337259 - LC337260					Kai 2017

<i>Petroschmidtia (Lycodes) sadoensis</i>	KC748103					Kwun, Kim 2013
<i>Petroschmidtia (Lycodes) sadoensis</i>					MT270440	Jang, Kim 2020
<i>Petroschmidtia toyamensis</i>	LC514670					Sakuma 2019
<i>Petroschmidtia (Lycodes) toyamensis</i>					AP004448	Miya et al. 2003
<i>Zoarcetes americanus</i>	MN883273 - MN883274		MN883214			Stoeckle et al. 2020
<i>Zoarcetes americanus</i>	KF930548 - KF930549					Bentley, Wiley 2013
<i>Zoarcetes americanus</i>	KC016047 - KC016058					McCusker et al. 2013
<i>Zoarcetes americanus</i>	GQ844846 - GQ844848					Radchenko et al. 2010
<i>Zoarcetes andriashevi</i>	KP100787 - KP100789					Radchenko et al. 2015
<i>Zoarcetes andriashevi</i>	KC751866 - KC751870					Turanov et al. 2014
<i>Zoarcetes andriashevi</i>	FJ744389 - FJ744392					Radchenko et al. 2010
<i>Zoarcetes elongatus (cf. gillii)</i>	KU236849 - KU236854, KY275323 - KY275324, KY275326					Wang et al. 2018
<i>Zoarcetes elongatus</i>	KU236852 - KU236854, KP100759 - KP100768	KP100693 - KP100714		KP100727 - KP100747		Radchenko et al. 2015
<i>Zoarcetes elongatus</i>		FJ744393 -		FJ798747 -		Radchenko et al. 2010

		FJ744402		FJ798755, GQ844859		
<i>Zoarces elongatus</i>		KC517324 - KC517324		KC517331 - KC517332		Radchenko et al. 2013
<i>Zoarces elongatus</i>			LC340206			Miya, Sado, 2017
<i>Zoarces elongatus</i>			LC579172			Miya et al. 2020
<i>Zoarces fedorovi</i>	KP100780 - KP100786, KC517319 - KC517323					Radchenko et al. 2015
<i>Zoarces gillii</i>	MK560604 - MK560605					Kim, Bae 2019
<i>Zoarces gillii</i>	KC748106			KC748078		Kwun, Kim 2013
<i>Zoarces gillii</i>					OK328172	Wang, Zheng 2021
<i>Zoarces gillii</i>					ON959145	Yan 2022
<i>Zoarces gillii</i>	GQ844844 - GQ844845	GQ844852 - GQ844853		GQ844854 - GQ844855		Radchenko et al. 2010
<i>Zoarces gillii</i>			LC069639, LC069638			Miya, Sado, 2015
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>	KJ205263					Knebelsberger et al. 2014
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>	KJ128662- KJ128664			KJ128946		Bergsten et al. 2014
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>	EF208062 - EF208064					Radchenko et al. 2008b
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>			U90403			Stepien et al. 1997
<i>Zoarces viviparus</i>		MT737181				Laakkonen et al. 2020

The misidentified mitogenomes of *Lycodes raridens* (MN604279) and *L. ygreknotatus* (LC093396) are highlighted in bold.

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